

DELIVERABLE

D.2.1.3. – IDENTIFICATION OF GAP OF KNOWLEDGE REGARDING MISSING/NOT VALIDATED INDICATORS, BROILERS WELFARE ON FARM.

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1. Introduction

This document is part of the **sub-activity 2.1** “*Relevant animal welfare indicators*” and concerns to the priority area related to the broilers welfare on farm. Here, the possible gaps of knowledge and ‘open norms’ are identified and discussed.

Definitions

Legal requirement: a requisite of the EU legislation to be assessed during the official controls.

Example: Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 16, Paragraph 4: “The frequency of the checks shall take into account the main risk factors, such as changes regarding the types or the size of animals slaughtered, or personnel working patterns and shall be established so as to ensure results with a high level of confidence.”

Gap of knowledge: lack of technical and scientific information of the indicators or its method.

Open-norm: requirement in the EU legislation which does not unambiguously translate into qualitative or quantitative criteria that can be used to check/verify compliance.

2. Methodology used

The information has been retrieved from questionnaires sent to the Competent Authorities (CAs) or from workshops that had taken place during a meeting between EURCAW-Poultry-SFA and Competent Authorities in September 2020 in Nice (France): broiler welfare on farm.

3. Broiler welfare on farm

3.1. Legal requirement: “*Animals shall be cared for by a sufficient number of staff*” (Directive 98/58/EC, Annex, Paragraph 1).

It is difficult to define what should be the sufficient number of staff since this is related to many factors such as farm layout, technology, staff quality etc.

To our knowledge there is no available literature providing information on the correct number of staff regarding the size of the barn and the number of animals. However, the integrated poultry companies in agreements with contract farmers require a certain number of staff in relation to the size of the farm so, although this is not supported by scientific literature it is recommended for practical use.

There are no specific ABIs although there is an exhausting list of indirect ABIs (number of dead chickens, decomposed carcasses, runts and stunts, injured birds, sick birds, flighty animals) that can be used as non-specific indicators to verify if the animals are sufficiently cared for, integrated with MBIs (such as wet litter areas, leaking drinkers, lack of feed in the feeders, dust levels, noxious gas concentrations).

There is a need for a method to evaluate whether there is a sufficient number of staff (animals are sufficiently cared for) that could be based on the use of a checklist of iceberg indicators.

3.2. Legal requirement: *“The keeper of the chickens shall hold a certificate which is recognised by the competent authority of the Member State concerned, attesting to the completion of such a training course or to having acquired experience equivalent to such training”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Article 4).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.3. Legal requirement: *“The owner or keeper shall provide instructions and guidance on the relevant animal welfare requirements, including those concerning the methods of culling practised in holdings, to persons employed or engaged by them to attend to chickens or to catch and load them”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Article 4).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement in relation to the need to provide written instructions and guidance.

The question is different related to the quality and reliability of the instructions and guidance provided. Directive 2007/43 EC, Article 8. Requires that: *“Member States shall encourage the development of guides to good management practice which shall include guidance on compliance with this Directive. The dissemination and use of such guides shall be encouraged”* but there are no indications on quality assessment of such guidance.

3.4. Legal requirement: *“All chickens kept on the holding must be inspected at least twice a day. Special attention should be paid to signs indicating a reduced level of animal welfare and/or animal health”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex 1, Paragraph 8).

There are no gaps of knowledge.

3.5. Legal requirement: *“Chickens that are seriously injured or show evident signs of health disorder, such as those having difficulties in walking, severe ascites or severe malformations, and are likely to suffer, shall receive appropriate treatment or be culled immediately”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 9).

This legal requirement is easily assessed based on records, but the farmer’s declaration could not be accurate and needs to be confirmed based on direct ABI observations.

3.6. Legal requirement: *“A veterinarian shall be contacted whenever necessary”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 9).

This legal requirement shows a gap due to the affirmation *“whenever necessary”*. This is an **open norm** (requirement in the EU legislation which does not unambiguously translate into qualitative or quantitative criteria that can be used to check/verify compliance) and we are not able to define objectively when a veterinarian should be contacted.

3.7. Legal requirement: *“Animals must be fed a wholesome diet which is appropriate to their age and species and which is fed to them in sufficient quantity to maintain them in good health and satisfy their nutritional needs”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 14).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.8. Legal requirement: *“All animals must have access to feed at intervals appropriate to their physiological need”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 15).

As broilers are fed *ad libitum* this requirement is not applicable. It is easy to verify feeding intervals but “appropriate to physiological needs” must be defined. Fasting is permitted by EU legislation for up to 12h, but physiological needs will differ according in particular to the age of the birds.

3.9. Legal requirement: *“Feed shall be either continuously available or be meal fed and must not be withdrawn from chickens more than 12 hours before the expected slaughter time”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 2).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.10. Legal requirement: *“All animals must have access to a suitable water supply or be able to satisfy their fluid intake needs by other means”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 16 - Directive 98/83/CE, Annex II).

There is no method to assess the animals comply with their physiological need of water.

3.11. Legal requirement: *“Drinkers shall be positioned and maintained in such a way that spillage is*

There is the need to define an acceptable level of wetness below drinker lines.

3.12. Legal requirement: *“All chickens shall have permanent access to litter which is dry and friable on the surface”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 3).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.13. Legal requirement: *“Materials to be used for the construction of accommodation, and in particular for the construction of pens and equipment with which the animals may come into contact, must not be harmful to the animals and must be capable of being thoroughly cleaned and disinfected. Accommodation and fittings for securing animals shall be constructed and maintained so that there are no sharp edges or protrusions likely to cause injury to the animals”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraphs 8-9).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.14. Legal requirement: *“The freedom of movement of an animal, having regard to its species and in accordance with established experience and scientific knowledge, must not be restricted in such a way as to cause it unnecessary suffering or injury”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 7).

Member States shall ensure that the maximum stocking density in a holding or a house of a holding does not at any time exceed 33 kg/m². When a derogation is granted under paragraph 3, the maximum stocking density in a holding or a house of a holding does not at any time exceed 39 kg/m². When the criteria set out in Annex V are fulfilled, Member States may allow that the maximum stocking

density referred to in paragraph 4 be increased by a maximum of 3 kg/m² (Directive 2007/43 EC, Article 3).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.15. Legal requirement: *“Feeding equipment must be designed, constructed and placed so that contamination of food and the harmful effects of competition between the animals are minimised” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraphs 14, 15 and 17).*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.16. Legal requirement: *“Watering equipment must be designed, constructed and placed so that contamination of water and the harmful effects of competition between the animals are minimised” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraphs 16 and 17).*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.17. Legal requirement: *“Where necessary sick or injured animals shall be isolated in suitable accommodation with, where appropriate, dry comfortable bedding” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 4).*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.18. Legal requirement: *“[...] temperature, relative air humidity [...] must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 10).*

Ventilation shall be sufficient to avoid overheating and, where necessary, in combination with heating systems to remove excessive moisture” (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 4).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.19. Legal requirement: *“Requirements for the use of higher stocking densities: The owner or keeper shall ensure that each house of a holding is equipped with ventilation and, if necessary, heating and cooling systems designed, constructed and operated in such a way that: [...]; (b) the inside temperature, when the outside temperature measured in the shade exceeds 30° C, does not exceed this outside temperature by more than 3° C; (c) the average relative humidity measured inside the house during 48 hours does not exceed 70 %*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.20. Legal requirement: *“[...] gas concentrations must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 10).*

There are no gaps of knowledge for this requirement.

3.21. Legal requirement: *“Requirements for the use of higher stocking densities: The owner or keeper shall ensure that each house of a holding is equipped with ventilation and, if necessary, heating and cooling systems designed, constructed and operated in such a way*

that: (a) the concentration of ammonia (NH₃) does not exceed 20 ppm and the concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) does not exceed 3000 ppm measured at the level of the chickens' heads" (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex II, Paragraph 3).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.22. Legal requirement: "[...] dust levels must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals" (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 10).

This legal requirement speaks about "harmful limits" to the animals and it is a problematic to clearly define them.

3.23. Legal requirement: *"All buildings shall have lighting with an intensity of at least 20 lux during the lighting periods, measured at bird eye level and illuminating at least 80% of the usable area. A temporary reduction in the lighting level may be allowed when necessary following veterinary advice" (Directive 2007/43 EU, Annex I, Paragraph 6).*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.24. Legal requirement: *"Animals kept in buildings must not be kept either in permanent darkness or without an appropriate period of rest from artificial lighting. Within seven days from the time when the chickens are placed in the building and until three days before the foreseen time of slaughter, the lighting must follow a 24-hour rhythm and include periods of darkness lasting at least six hours in total, with at least one uninterrupted period of darkness of at least four hours, excluding dimming periods" (Directive 98/58 EU, Annex, Paragraph 11 - Directive 2007/43 EU, Annex I, Paragraph 7).*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.25. Legal requirement: *"The sound level shall be minimised. Ventilation fans, feeding machinery or other equipment shall be constructed, placed, operated and maintained in such a way that they cause the least possible amount of noise" (Directive 2007/43 EU, Annex I, Paragraph 5).*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.26. Legal requirement: *"All surgical interventions carried out for reasons other than therapeutic or diagnostic purposes which result in damage to or the loss of a sensitive part of the body or the alteration of bone structure shall be prohibited" (Directive 2007/43 EU, Annex I, Paragraph 12).*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.27. Legal requirement: *"Beak trimming may be authorised by Member States when other measures to prevent feather pecking and cannibalism are exhausted. In addition, Member States may authorise the castration of chickens" (Directive 2007/43 EU, Annex I, Paragraph 12).*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.28. Legal requirement: *“In such cases, if [beak trimming] shall be carried out only after consultation and on the advice of a veterinarian and shall be carried out by qualified staff on chickens that are less than 10 days old. [...] The castration shall only be carried out under veterinary supervision by personnel who have received a specific training”* (Directive 2007/43 EU, Annex I, Paragraph 12).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.29. Legal requirement: *“Adequate lighting (fixed or portable) shall be available to enable the animals to be thoroughly inspected at any time”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 3).

There is are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.30. Legal requirement: *“All automated or mechanical equipment essential for the health and well-being of the animals must be inspected at least once daily”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 13).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.31. Legal requirement: *“Where defects are discovered, these must be rectified immediately, or if this is impossible, appropriate steps must be taken to safeguard the health and well-being of the animals”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 13).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.32. Legal requirement: *“In the event of failure of the [ventilation] system an alarm system must be provided to give warning of breakdown. The alarm system must be tested regularly”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 13).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.33. Legal requirement: *“Where the health and well-being of the animals is dependent on an artificial ventilation system, provision must be made for an appropriate backup system to guarantee sufficient air renewal to preserve the health and well-being of the animals”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 13).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.34. Legal requirement: *“The owner or keeper of the animals shall maintain a record of any medical treatment given and of the number of mortalities found to each inspection. The register of the medical treatments must be retained for a period of at least five years”* (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 5).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.35. Legal requirement: *“The owner or keeper shall maintain a record for each house of a holding of: (a) the number of chickens introduced; (b) the useable area; (c) the hybrid or breed of the*

chickens, if known; (d) by each control, the number of birds found dead with an indication of the causes, if known as well as the number of birds culled with cause; (e) the number of chickens remaining in the flock following the removal of chickens for sale or for slaughter” (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 11).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.36. Legal requirement: *“Those records [Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 11] shall be retained for a period of at least three years and shall be made available to the competent authority when carrying out an inspection or when otherwise requested” (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex I, Paragraph 11).*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.37. Legal requirement: *“Member States shall encourage the development of guides to good management practice which shall include guidance on compliance with this Directive. The dissemination and use of such guides shall be encouraged” (Directive 2007/43 EC, Article 8)*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.38. Legal requirement: *“No other substance, with the exception of those given for therapeutic, or prophylactic purposes or for the purposes of zootechnical treatment as defined in Article 1(2)(c) of Directive 96/22/EEC (1), must be administered to an animal unless it has been demonstrated by scientific studies of animal welfare or established experience that the effect of that substance is not detrimental to the health or welfare of the animal” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 18).*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.39. Legal requirement: *“Requirements for the use of higher stocking densities (>33 kg/m²): The owner or keeper shall maintain and have available in the house compiled documentation describing in detail the production systems. In particular it shall include information on technical details of the house and its equipment such as: (a) a plan of the house including the dimensions of the surfaces occupied by the chickens; (b) ventilation and, if relevant, cooling and heating system, including their location, a ventilation plan, detailing target air quality parameters, such as airflow, air speed and temperature; (c) feeding and watering systems and their location; (d) alarm systems and backup systems in the event of a failure of any automated or mechanical equipment essential for the health and well-being of the animals; (e) floor type and litter normally used” (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex II, Paragraph 2).*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.40. Legal requirement: *“Criteria for the use of increased stocking density (up to 42 kg/m²): Criteria: (a) the monitoring of the holding carried out by the competent authority within the last two years did not reveal any deficiencies with respect to the requirements of this Directive, and (b) the monitoring by the owner or keeper of the holding is carried*

out using the guides to good management practice referred to in Article 8, and (c) in at least seven consecutive, subsequently checked flocks from a house the cumulative daily mortality rate was below $1\% + 0,06\%$ multiplied by the slaughter age of the flock in days” (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex V, Paragraph 1).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.41. Legal requirement: *“In the case of stocking densities higher than 33 kg/m², the documentation accompanying the flock shall include the daily mortality rate and the cumulative daily mortality rate calculated by the owner or keeper and the hybrid or breed of the chickens. [...] These data as well as the number of broilers dead on arrival shall be recorded, indicating the holding and the house of the holding”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex III, Paragraph 1).

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

3.42. Legal requirement: *“In the context of the controls performed under the Regulation (EC) No 854/2004, the official veterinarian shall evaluate the results of the post-mortem inspection to identify other possible indications of poor welfare conditions such as abnormal levels of contact dermatitis, parasitism and systemic illness in the holding or the unit of the house of the holding of origin”* (Directive 2007/43 EC, Annex III, Paragraph 2).

There is no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement

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